

Investigation of Treacle's Effects for Cohesive Soil Stabilization

Azhar Abbas¹, Xie Xiongyao^{1*}, Ali Zar², Muhammad Yousaf³, Muhammad Gul Nawaz³

¹Department of Geotechnical Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai, 200092, China

²School of Hydraulic Engineering, Faculty of Infrastructure Engineering, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, P. R. China

³Department of Civil Engineering, University of Engineering and Technology Lahore, Pakistan

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*Corresponding Author:

Xie Xiongyao
xiexiongyao@tongji.edu.cn
Tel.: +86-021-65983479

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Natural soils have flaws in terms of workability, so it's critical to implement experimental techniques to increase soil workability and meet construction demands. Stabilization is essential for construction objectives such as enhancing the soil's carrying capacity, overcoming swelling issues in expansive soil, and so on. In this paper, we look at how treacle can be used to strengthen cohesive soil. We evaluated the geotechnical parameters of stabilized and unstabilized soil to see if the stabilizer had an influence on cohesive soil. On both stabilized soil and native soil samples, the following tests were performed: Atterberg's limit test, shrinkage test, Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) test, California Bearing Ration (CBR) test, and swelling test. Cohesive soil with treacle, whether or not it can be used as a stabilizing agent for coherent soil, has been experimentally examined for determining soil strength properties. Finally, the amount of treacle that is effective as a stabilizing agent, treacle quality measures, soil stabilizing lab trials, and other requirements for further positive progress on this idea for cohesive soil improvements are explored.

Keywords: TREACLE; WORKABILITY; BEARING CAPACITY; EXPENSIVE SOILS; CALIFORNIA BEARING RATION (CBR) TEST; UNCONFINED COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH (UCS) TEST; ATTERBERG'S LIMIT TEST; STABILIZING AGENT

1. Introduction

Clay soils are found all over the world; their prevalence is not climate-dependent; however, they are more common in dry and semi-arid climates. Due to their tendency to heave during the wet season and

shrink during the dry season, this condition is troublesome for engineering constructions (1). Expanded soil is a worldwide phenomenon that causes numerous issues for civil engineers (2). They are regarded as a possible natural hazard that, if not adequately controlled, can result in substantial structural damage (3). Expansive soils, more than any other natural hazard, including earthquakes and floods, can cause more damage to structures, particularly lighter buildings and pavements (4). Many roads have collapsed prematurely as a result of

volumetric fluctuations in expanding clay soil. With rising global energy demand and rising local aggregate demand, removing inferior soils and replacing them with foreign soils has become materially costly (5,6). Stabilization of the soil serves three purposes. The first is to increase the strength of the soil to increase its load-bearing capacity, and the second is to manage dust by binding soil particles together and removing or reducing dust produced by equipment and aircraft activity in dry weather or in arid locations. The third is soil waterproofing, which prevents surf entry and maintains the natural or manufactured strength of soil (6,7). Stabilization of the expanding clay soil with various additions could be one method to reduce the problem. Most typical stabilizing agents, on the other hand, are relatively expensive to integrate (7,8). As a result, it's critical to alter the qualities of locally accessible soil to the point where it can be used in road construction, as well as to maximize the usage of various industrial by-products like treacle as a soil modifying/stabilizing agent (9). The stabilization of the expanding clay soil using various additions could be one method to reduce the problem (3). Most typical stabilizing agents, on the other hand, are relatively expensive to integrate (7,8). The feasibility of employing recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) to improve the shear/compressive strengths and deformation properties of clay soils is evaluated experimentally (10). To investigate the optimal combination of Nano-Silica and Polypropylene fiber with clay soil, researchers looked at the effect of recycled polypropylene fiber (PPF), which is generated during the manufacturing of plastic chairs, as well as Nano-Silica as a novel technique to enhance the mechanical characteristics of clay soil (11). A unique contribution to the theoretical understanding of clayey materials' cyclic response, demonstrating significant validation of an advanced kinematic hardening model versus laboratory data on a variety of natural and compacted clays in the literature (12). Soil-lime stabilization is a soil-stabilization process that involves mixing soil with lime. Lime is a great short-term soil alteration option (13). The term "soil cement stabilization" refers to soil stabilization that includes cement (3). Soil cement is made by mixing crushed soil with a certain amount of cement and water, compacting it to the proper density, and curing it (14). Test results revealed that increasing the water-cement ratio resulted in a decrease in the strength of the cement-stabilized soil (3). The impact of soil parameters and mineralogy on the geo-mechanical behavior of several types of clay soils treated with geopolymers was examined in depth (15).

Fly ash is a by-product of coal combustion in power plants. Fly ash is classified as pozzolanic because it contains silica, alumina and calcium oxides, iron oxide, and alkalis. A rising variety of non-traditional additives have been developed for soil stabilization (16). Salts, acids, enzymes, lignosulfonates, emulsions, polymers, tree resins, treacle, and geo-fibers are among the non-traditional stabilizers that can be grouped into several key categories. The maximum dry soil density increased from (1.85-1.92) gcm⁻³ with an increase in a soil sample treated with 8% NaCl (17,18), and the unconfined compressive strength of soil treated with 8% NaCl increased up to 700kN/m². This could be useful for long-term highway pavement subgrade applications. Currently, laboratory tests are being undertaken to explore the effect of various chloride compounds, such as NaCl, MgCl₂, and CaCl₂, on the engineering qualities of silt and clay soil (19). Polymers are made up of hydrocarbon chains that are linked together within soil particles to have a stabilizing effect (18). Polymers act as a binder, collecting soil particles and stabilizing the soil matrix. Unconfined compressive strength testing was performed on lean

clay and fat clay treated with various natural and synthetic polymers (20). Electro-osmosis has an effect on the chemical, physical, and mechanical responses of clay soil in laboratory investigations (1,21). Using cane molasses as the carbon source, *Sphingomonas* sp. FM-01 was used to generate welan-gum successfully. The molasses-welan gum mixture had an appropriate molecular weight, equivalent rheological properties, and greater viscosity stability than sucrose, indicating that cane molasses might be studied as a feasible and economical substrate for cost-effective welan gum manufacturing (22). As a result, it's crucial to think about how treacle is handled and disposed of, especially in instances where supply exceeds demand. It is possible, especially if the industrial usage of treacle is not diversified. Sugar manufacturers commonly employ cane treacle as a dust suppressant on roads within their premises (23,24). Nowadays, synthetic and low-cost carbon sources are being used in batch and fed batch fermentation to boost biomass and lipid production from oleaginous yeast strains. Plasticizer (or water-reducing admixture) use in recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) lowers water demand, improves workability, and increases mechanical strength and durability. Molasses and dark fermentation effluent were also solidified with agar and used for dark and photo-fermentation to produce H₂ (25). The solid jelly form of molasses allowed for a slow release of substrate into the liquid broth during dark fermentation, preventing rapid pH drop. The technique of soil stabilization of expansive soils with treacle has only been studied in a few studies (25–27). To understand the mechanism and geo-engineering properties of expansive soils stabilized by sugar cane treacle, more research is required.

The purpose of this study is to see if sugar cane treacle can be used to stabilize expansive clay soils that aren't suited for sub-grade pavement by enhancing bearing capacity and lowering swelling potential. The goal of this study is to explore the response of expansive clay soils by using a mixture of sugar cane treacle at various concentrations. Regular laboratory testing, strength tests, volume tests, and stability tests will be used to establish the geotechnical engineering parameters of the natural expansive clay soil. The California Bearing Ratio (CBR), Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS), and swell testing were used to measure the strength and volume stability effect of native expansive clay soils and expansive clay soils enriched with cane treacle alone (28–30).

The goal of this study is to see how expansive clay soil reacts when different amounts of sugar cane treacle are added. In the second part, experimental conditions and explanations will be conducted, and a sufficient number of treacle results and discussion will be handled in the third part, along with the restrictions discovered. Conclusions and potential enhancements will be summarized in the end.

2. Materials and methods

Individual soil particles are bonded together by water films in fine-grained soils (31). Regardless of the applied external force, cohesion is higher in well-compacted clays (32). When evaluating the sliding resistance of soil mass grain particles, the value of the internal friction angle is almost independent of the normal pressure. Coarse gravel has no capillary rise; coarse sand has up to 30 cm of capillary rise; fine sand and soils have up to 1.2 m of capillary rise; and dry sand has very little capillary rise. Capillary rises of up to 1.2 meters are possible in clays, although pure clays are useless (33,34). The permeability of a soil is the rate at which water flows through it under

hydraulic gradient action. The flow rate and the water head have a direct relationship. The total bulk of the soil, not the number of individual particles, determines permeability (32). When a load is given to a soil, it reduces its volume (or structure and bulk), but when the weight is removed, the soil recovers to its original volume. The most important feature of the soil's elastic behavior is that it does not become permanently deformed no matter how many load repetitions are applied to it as long as the applied stress does not exceed the yield stress. Elasticity is a property of this type of peat (28). Gravels, sands, and silts are incompressible, which means that no observable volume shift occurs when a moist mass of these materials is crushed. Sand and silt compressibility varies with clay density, whereas sand and silt compressibility varies directly with water content (33,34).

2.1 Consistency Limits/ Atterberg Limits

The Atterberg limits, also known as shrinkage, plastic, and liquid limits, are a simple estimate of fine-grained soil's actual water content. Soil absorbs increasing amounts of water, it undergoes different changes in behavior and consistency as time (35). Figure 1 depicts a quick summary of Atterberg's limit.

Figure 1. Atterberg's Limits(35)

The Liquid Limit (LL) is defined as the moisture content at which soil begins to behave like a liquid material and start to flow. The LL of a fine-grained soil supply the moisture content at which the soil's shear strength is roughly 2.5kN/m^2 (36). The apparatus used by Casagrande to determine the liquid limit experimentally is depicted in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Liquid Limit Determination: Casagrande's Apparatus

The Plastic Limit (PL) is the moisture level at which soil begins to behave like a plastic material. Figure 3 depicts a perspective of a lab experiment for determining PL. The index of plasticity (PI) is described by ASTM D-4318-17 as (36):

$$PI = LL - PL \quad (1)$$

Figure 3. Plastic Limit Determination

The Shrinkage Limit (SL) is the moisture level at which no more volume changes occur with further moisture reduction [41]. The density of a substance is compared to the density of a reference substance to determine its specific gravity. Table 1 shows the specific gravity of several soil types. It is the ratio of a substance's mass to the mass of a reference substance for the same volume provided (36).

Table 1. Typical Values of Specific Gravity of Soil (16,37)

Type of Soils	Specific gravity
Sand	2.65-2.67
Silty Sand	2.67-2.70
Inorganic Sand	2.70-2.80
Soils with mica and iron	2.75-3.00
Organic soils	Variable but maybe under 2.0

In engineering, shear strength refers to a material's or component's resistance to yield or structural failure when shear fails in the material or component, as depicted in Figure 4. A material's shear load is a force that causes a sliding failure in a plane parallel to the force's course. The soil, water, and air distribution in a stack of soil mass is demonstrated in Figure 5 (38–40).

Figure 4. Shear Forces

Figure 5. Soil volume (s-soil (dry), v-void (pores filled with water or air), w-water, a-air. V is volume, M is mass.)

2.2 Bearing Capacity of Soil

In geotechnical engineering, bearing capacity refers to the strength of soil to withstand loads applied to the ground. The overall average contact pressure between the foundation and the soil that is not expected to produce shear failure in the soil is known as soil carrying capability. In engineering, shear strength refers to a material's or component's resistance to yielding or structural failure. The term "settlement" refers to the downward movement of the ground caused by a load that compacts the soil underneath it (38). The ground's downward motion surrounding an excavated room is also referred to as settlement. All fine-grained soils with a saturation degree of less than 90%, including silts and clays, are submitted to quick settling examination. The permeability coefficient of all coarse-grained soils is high (say, above 10.2 m/s). Consolidation agreements are time-sensitive, and revisions might take months or even years to implement. For more than 700 years, the leaning tower of Pisa in Italy has been undergoing consolidation settlement. On one hand, the lean is triggered by a higher settlement due to restructuring. The primary settlements are created in 3 to 10 years for most endeavors (38).

When highly plastic soil ($LL > 50-70$) is treated with a calcium-rich additive, the chemical reaction between the clay particles and the additive leads to a reduction in the size of the double-layer diffusion and an increase in particle contact. As the plastic limit (PL) of the soil grows, the liquid limit (LL) of the soil drops, lowering the plasticity index of the stabilized soil (PI). The stabilized soil's strength or stiffness will be increased. The impact of cement addition on expansive clay soil plasticity by altering cement amount and discovered that as cement content increased, LL reduced and PL increased. As a result, PI was reduced by up to 14% by increasing cement content, and subsequently increased by adding more cement. A change in the chemical composition of the soil can be noticed by reducing maximum dry density (MDD) and increasing optimum moisture content (OMC) of the soil-stabilizer mixture. According to the compaction test results of cement-treated soil, there was a somewhat different observation from MDD and OMC due to the increase in stabilizer content. Because of the little amount of cement used and the slow hydration process, improvements in the MDD and OMC were considered insignificant (15,32,36).

2.3. Laboratory Testing Procedures

2.3.1. Moisture content determination by oven drying method

Weigh some empty containers after filling them with water (W_1). The soil sample was taken at three different depths from the ground: 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 meters. Fill the jar halfway with soil samples and weigh them (W_2) to the accuracy of 0.01 g. If the balance is insufficient, cover the samples immediately. In an oven, the samples were roasted for 24 hours at 110°C (± 5 degrees Celsius). Take the oven-dried samples out of the oven and weigh them (W_3). Equations 2 and 3 can be used to compute the weight of water and soil. Using equation no. 4, calculate the moisture content (41).

$$W_w = W_2 - W_3 \quad (2)$$

$$W_s = W_2 - W_1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Moisture Content} = w = W_w / W_s * 100 \quad (4)$$

2.3.2. Sieve Analysis

Take the weight of some empty containers and record it (W_1). The soil sample was taken at different depths of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 meters from the ground. Place soil samples in the container and report the weight (W_2) to 0.01 g accuracy. Then cover the samples immediately. The samples should then be covered as soon as possible. If a balance isn't enough, bake the samples for 24 hours at 110°C ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). Remove the samples from the oven and weigh them after they have been dried in the oven (42).

2.3.3. Liquid Limit determination

Plot the relationship between the water content (W_n) and the equivalent number of drops (N), on a semi-logarithmic graph. Draw a straight line connecting the three or more plotted points that is as straight as possible. Use the water content corresponding to the line's 25-drop abscissa junction as the soil and ground liquid cap to get the closest total value. For fitting a straight line to the data and finding the liquid boundary, numerical approaches can be employed instead of the graphical approach (43).

One-point method: $LL = W_n (N/25)^{0.121}$. For the one-point method, no. of blows should be between 20 and 30 (43).

2.3.4. Plastic Limit Determination

Weight of empty container = W_1 ,

Weight of empty container + wet soil = W_2 ,

Weight of empty container + dry soil = W_3 ,

Weight of Water = $W_w = W_2 - W_1$, Weight of soil solids = $W_s = W_3 - W_1$,

Moisture Content = $w = W_w / W_s * 100$, Plastic Limit = w ,

2.3.5. Specific Gravity Test

Specific gravity can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Specific gravity} = (W_2 - W_1) / a / [(W_4 - W_1) - (W_3 - W_2)] \quad (5)$$

a = temperature correction coefficient

2.3.6. Unconfined Compression Test

Figure 6. (a) Unconfined Compression Device, (b) graphical explanation

The diagram of the UCS testing machine is shown in Figure 6. Calculate the unit's strain, the area corrected, and the unit's stress to have enough measurements to appropriately characterize the stress-strain curve. Trace the data on graph paper with stress, Q_u , and pressure on the y-axis and x-axis, respectively. Draw Mohr's circle with the average Q_u to show soil cohesiveness (39,40,44).

2.3.7. CBR Test

It's the force required per unit area to puncture a soil mass at 1.25 mm/min using a typical circular piston. California Bearing Ratio Test (CBR) testing is essential for the standard material to penetrate enough. The California State Highway Department (USA) established the CBR Test to measure subgrade soil carrying ability for adaptable pavement design (38). Tests are conducted in wet or dry conditions on natural or compacted soils, with the results compared to established test curves to assess the subgrade's soil strength (45).

2.4. AASHTO Soil Classification System

The AASHTO (American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials) system is used in highway projects (37). It's also widely used to see if soils are suitable for supporting roadway pavements in such projects. Both grain-size distribution and Atterberg limit data are employed in the AASHTO methodology (37). This categorization goes from A-1 (the best soils) to A-8 (the worst soils) (worst soils). Soils with a community index of less than 20 are healthy, while soils with a score of more than 20 are severely unhealthy. Land that is "great" for us as a highway subgrade, on the other hand, may be "quite awful" for other uses. The gadget can pass through a 3-inch sieve with only a little amount of soil. If any material fails to pass through the 3-inch sieve, the weight % of that item should be reported and indicated with the classification (37). Figure 7 shows how to calculate the classification. Begin on the left side with A-1-a soils and check each requirement to determine which group it belongs to. If any of the conditions aren't met, move to the right. Repeat the procedure till you've completed all of the steps. Do not start the map in the middle. The group index can be calculated using the following equation (46,47):

$$\text{Group Index} = (F-35) [0.2 + 0.005(wL-40)] + 0.01(F-15) (\text{IP} -10) \quad (6)$$

Calculate the group index for A-2-6 or A-2-7 soils by simply adding the second term to the calculation. For all soils, assign a fixed number to the community index (37,47). The calculated group index should be presented as zero if the values are less than zero. Finally, display the AASHTO soil classification as an A-1 to A-8 category

classification, with the category index in brackets. A-4(20) is the code for soil having an A-4 group classification and a 20-group index (37,43,47).

General classification	Granular materials (35% or less of total sample passing No. 200)						
	A-1			A-2			
Group classification	A-1-a	A-1-b	A-3	A-2-4	A-2-5	A-2-6	A-2-7
Sieve analysis (percent passing)							
No. 10	50 max.		51 min.	35 max.	35 max.	35 max.	35 max.
No. 40	30 max.	50 max.	10 max.				
No. 200	15 max.	25 max.					
Characteristics of fraction passing No. 40							
Liquid limit				40 max.	41 min.	40 max.	41 min.
Plasticity index	6 max.		NP	10 max.	10 max.	11 min.	11 min.
Usual types of significant constituent materials	Stone fragments, gravel, and sand		Fine sand	Silty or clayey gravel and sand			
General subgrade rating	Excellent to good						

(a)

General classification	Silt-clay materials (more than 35% of total sample passing No. 200)			
	A-4	A-5	A-6	A-7
Group classification				A-7-5* A-7-6†
Sieve analysis (percent passing)				
No. 10				
No. 40				
No. 200	36 min.	36 min.	36 min.	36 min.
Characteristics of fraction passing No. 40				
Liquid limit	40 max.	41 min.	40 max.	41 min.
Plasticity index	10 max.	10 max.	11 min.	11 min.
Usual types of significant constituent materials	Silty soils		Clayey soils	
General subgrade rating	Fair to poor			

*For A-7-5, $PI \leq LL - 30$

†For A-7-6, $PI > LL - 30$

(b)

Figure 7. (a) AASHTO coarse-grained soil classification chart, **(b)** AASHTO fine-grained soil classification chart

2.5 Viscosity Test for Treacle

The following parameters should be used to calculate the viscosity of treacle (36,42,47):

- (a) undiluted treacle
- (b) constant temperature
- (c) constant concentration

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Consistency Limits

Consistency limits were established for soils treated with treacle. Table 2 shows the differences in consistency limits for various mixes as a result of different amounts of treacle in the soil. The soil was treated with different levels of treacle content ranging from 4% to 12% for 14 days, followed by a 4% increase and cure. As shown in Fig. 8, the soil LL decreased by up to 8% with an increment in treacle content, then increased with an increase in treacle content.

Table 2. Liquid Limit effect with Treacle percentage

Treacle (%)	Liquid limit
0	58
4	45.82
8	42.67
12	48

Figure 8. Liquid Limit Vs Treacle

Untreated soil's plastic limit (PL) was calculated to be 27.125 %, and it did not change significantly as the treacle content increased. The PI for treacle-treated soils ranged from 27.125 % to around 33 percent for 0%, 4%, 6%, 8%, and 12% of treacle in total soil mass, respectively. When treacle is applied to expansive clay soil, it exchanges cat-ions and loses its adhesive property, resulting in a minor reduction in LL. Due to the large number of inorganic compounds that induce a cation exchange process in treacle, cat-ions exchange processes in the soil-treacle mixture are minimal. In addition to the electrochemical attraction, treacle was observed to increase the adhesion properties of aggregated soil particles.

3.2. Compaction characteristics of soil stabilization with treacle

The compaction characteristic curves calculated for the sample soils used in the experimental work are included in this study. In addition to the treated/stabilized soils, modified Proctor experiments were conducted on soils. Figure 11 shows the compaction curves for bare soil and treacle-treated/stabilized soils. As shown in Fig. 10, the MDD characteristics of sample soils treated with treacle closely resembles the traditional bell-shaped curve for moisture density. As shown in Figs. 10 and 9, the curves for untreated soil samples shifted to the left, indicating that adding treacle increased MDD while decreasing OMC.

TABLE 3. Treacle effect vs Dry Density

Treacle (%)	Dry density (kN/m ³)	Optimum moisture (%)
0	18.03	25.3
4	18.26	23.33
8	18.83	23.02
12	18.29	23

Figure 9. OMC Vs Treacle

Figure 10. Dry Density Vs Treacle

Moreover, MDD values have been found to increase by up to 8% as treacle content increases, and MDD decreases as treacle content increases. Because treacle is positively charged and easily attracted to the surface of clay mineral particles due to their adhesive properties and attached soil particles, the density rises.

Figure 11. Compaction Vs Treacle

3.3. Effect of Treacle content on CBR Values

This section details the estimated CBR values for the experiment's sample soils. CBR experiments used both untreated soil samples and soils that had been treated with treacle to stabilize them. Stabilizer concentrations ranging from 1% to 12% were used in the tests. CBR results were obtained after 14 days for all samples treated with treacle cure and then soaked with 4.5 kg surcharge load for four days.

TABLE 4. Treacle effect on soil stabilization with CBR

Treacle (%)	CBR
0	1.25
4	8
8	9.5
12	7.5

Figure 12. CBR vs Treacle

The soil was treated with treacle using the ideal compaction test moisture content. The results are shown in Table 4, which show a significant increase in strength and CBR values for the two samples when compared to the untreated soil sample. CBR values of 9.5 percent for an 8% soil treatment and 1.25 percent for natural soil were reported. The findings show that the CBR of treated soil increases treacle content by up to 8%, then decreases as treacle content increases. As shown in Fig. 12, the highest CBR was found at around 8% treacle content. Increased CBR values in soils treated with treacle are caused by cat-ion exchange reactions and treacle with flocculation and agglomeration effects. During CBR testing, cane treacle caused a strong cementing bond to form between soil particles, which improved penetration resistance. Individual soil grains may be coated with treacle as the treacle content rises above a certain threshold, resulting in a decrease in CBR values.

3.4. CBR Swell of Expansive Clay Soils

Soil treated with treacle reduced CBR swelling. CBR swell was 2.62 percent, 2.54 percent, and 2.21 percent in soil treated with 4.0 percent, 8.0 percent, and 12 percent treacle, respectively. Figure 13 shows that soil treated with 8.0 percent treacle reduced CBR swell the most, which was considerably lower than natural soil.

Figure 13. Swell vs Treacle

3.5. Treacle's Impact on UCS Value

This section explains the UCS values for the sample soils used in the experiment. UCS tests were performed on treated and untreated remolded specimens in accordance with ASTM D-5102 (44). Untreated and

treated/stabilized soil trample stress-strain curves Table 5 and Fig. 15 shows the results of UCS tests on remolded, untreated specimens as well as remolded specimens treated with various treacle materials. The UCS values of treacle stabilized soil were found to increase with treacle content up to 8.0 percent before declining.

Table 5. UCS Values effect with Treacle (%)

Treacle added (%)	UCS value(psi)
0	21.0800
4	31.1840
8	40.4000
12	21.9600

FIGURE 14. UCS vs Treacle

Because the axial strain has increased dramatically with an increase in treacle content, treacle increases the strength of untreated soils while also strengthening their resilience or cohesive nature and making them more ductile. Figure 15 depicts typical stress-strain curves for soil specimens containing various amounts of treacle. With the addition of stabilizers, the stress-strain curves shifted to the right. This signifies that treacle makes soil more ductile than soils that have not been treated or sterilized. The increase in UCS values of soils treated with treacle can be attributed to the coating of individual soil grains with treacle, and the reduction in UCS values with an increase in treacle content above a certain limit can also be attributed to the coating of individual soil grains with treacle.

Figure 15. Unconfined Compression Test

4. Conclusion

The soils' unconfined compressive resistance and CBR value were both improved by using treacle. It's fair to say that treacle aided soil cohesion, resulting in higher unregulated compressive strength and penetration resistance during the CBR test. According to laboratory test results, the sugar cane treacle sample contained a small number of inorganic elements/compounds that cause a chemical reaction involving cat-ion exchange during stabilization with expansive clay soil. There was a noticeable difference in the soil that had been Treacle-treated. The soil treated with 8% treacle yielded a CBR value of 9.5 percent from 1.25 percent native soil. The expansive soil's strength improved significantly, with a UCS value of 40.4 psi compared to 20.08 psi for natural soil.

The following are the main recommendations based on the research findings. Because the composition of treacle is influenced by the soil in which sugar cane is grown and the method of sugar production, more research on the composition of sugar cane treacle in sugar factories around the world is recommended. The effect of sugar cane treacle length on the stabilization of expansive soil must be investigated. Because the stabilization of expansive soil with treacle mixture is a relatively new concept with limited progress, chemical interactions and mechanisms between sugar cane treacle, water, and expansive clay soil must be investigated. The effect of the curing cycle on soils treated with a treacle mixture must be investigated. Finally, the actual field output should be analyzed in the lab because this study was conducted on expansive clay soils that had only been treated with sugar cane treacle.

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